

DMP for the State Research Programme project "The Latvian Language in Time, Space, and Society (LaTS)"

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the project "The Latvian Language in Time, Space, and Society (LaTS)" (No. VPP-LETONIKA-2025/1-0012) outlines the principles and procedures for collecting, processing, storing, documenting, and disseminating the research data generated during the project. The project aims to strengthen and expand knowledge of Latvian as a dynamic linguistic system shaped by historical development, regional and social diversity, functional variation, and multilingual environments in Latvia and beyond, while also supporting the development of Latvian as a cornerstone of national identity and state security.

To achieve this goal, Latvian will be studied in six research dimensions: sociolinguistics, terminology and translation studies, dialectology and the study of the Latgalian written language, onomastics, the history of the Latvian language, and language acquisition. The project consists of six interrelated sub-projects that correspond to the research tasks defined in sub-paragraph 6.1.1 of the Cabinet Order No. 559 of 12 September 2025. Each sub-project generates and analyses linguistic data of different types, including lexicographic, corpus-based, dialectological, and onomastic material.

The research will rely on several established digital linguistic resources and platforms that serve both as primary sources and as infrastructures for data dissemination. These include the Latvian Historical Dictionary (lvvv.tezaurs.lv), the Corpus of Early Latvian Texts (<https://senie.korpuss.lv/>; Senie.lv), the Interactive Map of Latvian Dialects (dialekti.lu.lv), and citizen-science platforms for collecting linguistic data, such as vietvardi.lu.lv (place-name collection) and apvidvardi.lu.lv (regional vocabulary collection).

The purpose of this DMP is to ensure that all research data are managed according to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). It defines standards for metadata, documentation, storage, long-term preservation, and open access. The plan also addresses ethical considerations, intellectual property rights, and the responsible reuse of existing linguistic resources. Through careful data management, the project will contribute to the sustainability and further development of open linguistic infrastructures in Latvia.

In addition to supporting scientific research, the resulting datasets and enhanced digital resources will facilitate broader access to linguistic knowledge for researchers, educators, students, and policymakers. The project will therefore strengthen both the research infrastructure and the societal impact of Latvian linguistics.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

State Research Programme
“Letonika — Fostering a Latvian
and European Society”

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0002-3458-5890), Edmundas Trumpa (0000-0001-7965-1516), Everita Andronova (0000-0003-1865-4611), Gunita Arnava (0009-0002-6244-1808), Ieva Ozola (0009-0001-3269-6458), Irēna Ilga Jansone (0009-0003-4207-0963), Linda Lauze (0000-0003-3922-7774), Renāte Siliņa-Piņķe (orcid:0000-0002-5553-2165), Sanita Martena (Lazdiņa) (0000-0002-9116-6844), Velga Polinska (0000-0002-5459-1382), Māris Baltiņš, Agris Timuška, Anna Frīdenberga, Anna Vulāne, Brigita Bušmane, Bruno Georgs Rautenbergs, Elga Skrūzmane, Elīna Skreivere, Elīza Marija Rudzīte, Evelīna Ķiršakmene, Ilze Štrausa, Jānis Veckrācis, Justīne Bondare, Kristīne Mežapuķe, Lauma Pretkalniņa, Marita Silkāne, Pēteris Vanags, Regīna Kvašīte, Sanita Placēna, Sintija Ķauķīte, Vija Požarnova, Viktorija Prituļaka

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: DMP for the State Research Programme project "The Latvian Language in Time, Space, and Society (LaTS)"

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the project "The Latvian Language in Time, Space, and Society (LaTS)" (No. VPP-LETONIKA-2025/1-0012) outlines the principles and procedures for collecting, processing, storing, documenting, and disseminating the research data generated during the project. The project aims to strengthen and expand knowledge of Latvian as a dynamic linguistic system shaped by historical development, regional and social diversity, functional variation, and multilingual environments in Latvia and beyond, while also supporting the development of Latvian as a cornerstone of national identity and state security.

To achieve this goal, Latvian will be studied in six research dimensions: sociolinguistics, terminology and translation studies, dialectology and the study of the Latgalian written language, onomastics, the history of the Latvian language, and language acquisition. The project consists of six interrelated sub-projects that correspond to the research tasks defined in sub-paragraph 6.1.1 of the Cabinet Order No. 559 of 12 September 2025. Each sub-project generates and analyses linguistic data of different types, including lexicographic, corpus-based, dialectological, and onomastic material.

The research will rely on several established digital linguistic resources and platforms that serve both as primary sources and as infrastructures for data dissemination. These include the Latvian Historical Dictionary (lvvv.tezaurs.lv), the Corpus of Early Latvian Texts (<https://senie.korpuss.lv/>; Senie.lv), the Interactive Map of Latvian Dialects (dialekti.lu.lv), and citizen-science platforms for collecting linguistic data, such as vietvardi.lu.lv (place-name collection) and apvidvardi.lu.lv (regional vocabulary collection).

The purpose of this DMP is to ensure that all research data are managed according to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). It defines standards for metadata, documentation, storage, long-term preservation, and open access. The plan also addresses ethical considerations, intellectual property rights, and the responsible reuse of existing linguistic resources. Through careful data management, the project will contribute to the sustainability and further development of open linguistic infrastructures in Latvia.

In addition to supporting scientific research, the resulting datasets and enhanced digital resources will facilitate broader access to linguistic knowledge for researchers, educators, students, and policymakers. The project will therefore strengthen both the research infrastructure and the societal impact of Latvian linguistics.

Researchers:

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Organizations:
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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: State Research Programme "Letonika — Fostering a Latvian and European Society"

Project: The Latvian Language in Time, Space, and Society (LaTS)

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

The Corpus of Early Written Latvian

The Corpus of early written Latvian 'SENIE' provides access to the texts and facsimiles of written Latvian of the 16th–18th century. Its aim is to facilitate studies of early Latvian in general and to serve as the basis for 'The Historical dictionary of Latvian (16th–17th cc.)'. Corpus serves as a unique digital repository of early Latvian texts, whose physical copies are distributed all over the world. The Corpus contains digitised texts and facsimile images, accompanied by metadata and linguistic annotations. It was first launched in January 2003, and in 2017 it was converted to Unicode. The corpus is continuously maintained and expanded with newly identified sources and improved annotations, supporting research in historical linguistics, lexicography, and the history of Latvian written language.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data collection and generation is to create a structured digital corpus of early written Latvian texts from the 16th–18th centuries in order to support research on the history of the Latvian language and to provide the empirical basis for The Historical Dictionary of Latvian (16th–17th cc.).

The collected data enable systematic linguistic analysis of early Latvian, including lexical, morphological and orthographic variation, and support broader studies in historical linguistics and the history of written Latvian.

The data originate from historical printed sources and manuscripts preserved in libraries and archives in Latvia and abroad. These sources are digitised as facsimile images and transcribed into machine-readable texts, which are then structured and enriched with metadata for inclusion in the corpus.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

The corpus contains several types of data formats. The main data consist of digitised text files encoded in Unicode. In addition, the corpus includes facsimile images of historical sources and accompanying metadata describing the sources and their bibliographic information. Text data are stored in structured formats suitable for corpus processing and search systems, while images are stored in standard image formats. The use of Unicode encoding ensures long-term readability and compatibility with international standards.

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

CLARIN-LV repository

id: null, Type: handle

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data may be useful for researchers in historical linguistics, Baltic studies, lexicography, corpus linguistics, and digital humanities.

In particular, the corpus provides valuable linguistic evidence for studying the history of the Latvian language, including the development of vocabulary, morphology, and syntax in early written texts (16th–18th centuries).

The data are also relevant for lexicographic work, including the compilation of the Historical Dictionary of the Latvian Language, as well as for broader studies of early printed texts and language standardisation.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

Handle

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

CLARIN-LV repository

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

The corpus data are stored in the CLARIN-LV repository and are available for reuse according to the repository's access conditions and license. Therefore, the data remain usable by third parties after the end of the project.

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The dataset used in the project is deposited in the CLARIN-LV repository and is intended to remain available for long-term reuse. The repository ensures long-term preservation and access to the data according to its policies.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Anta Trumpa (0000-0001-6022-0433)

The sub-project leader oversees data management and compliance with the Data Management Plan.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Firewall

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Historical Dictionary of Latvian Language

The project develops the Historical Dictionary of the Latvian Language (LVVV), a corpus-based lexicographic resource documenting the vocabulary of early Latvian written texts. The dictionary is based on the Corpus of Early Written Latvian, which contains digitised sources from the 16th–18th centuries.

The aim of the dictionary is to describe the historical development of Latvian vocabulary, including meanings, grammatical information, etymology, and usage examples from the corpus. The resource is designed as an electronic dictionary that can be continuously expanded and updated as new sources are added to the corpus.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data generation is to compile and develop the Historical Dictionary of the Latvian Language (LVVV). The dictionary entries are created on the basis of lexical data extracted from the Corpus of Early Written Latvian, which contains digitised texts from the 16th–18th centuries. The collected and processed data provide information on historical vocabulary, meanings, grammatical features, etymology, and usage examples, supporting research on the development of the Latvian language.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

The data are stored and processed in structured digital formats. Dictionary entries are created in a lexicographic database environment (TLex).

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

CLARIN-LV repository

id: null, Type: handle

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data will be useful for researchers in historical linguistics, lexicography, Baltic studies, and digital humanities. The dictionary provides structured information on the historical vocabulary of the Latvian language, including meanings, grammatical information, etymology, and usage examples from early written texts. It will also be useful for historians, philologists, and anyone interested in the history of the Latvian language and culture.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

Handle

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

CLARIN-LV repository

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The data can be accessed through standard web browsers via the online platform of the *Historical Dictionary of the Latvian Language* (LVVV). Source texts and lexical data are accessed through the *Corpus of Early Written Latvian* and its search interface. The dictionary entries are created and managed using lexicographic software (TLex).

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

The data will be available to third parties through the online platform of the *Historical Dictionary of the Latvian Language (LVVV)*. As an electronic dictionary, it is designed to provide open access to historical lexical data and to support further research on the Latvian language and its history.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Anta Trumpa (0000-0001-6022-0433)

The sub-project leader oversees data management and compliance with the Data Management Plan.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Firewall

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Interactive Map of Latvian Dialects

The Interactive Map of Latvian Dialects is a digital platform that provides access to dialect data collected by the Institute of the Latvian Language. The resource integrates materials from dialect research, including data from dialect atlases, linguistic maps, fieldwork records, and audio recordings of dialect speech. The platform enables the geographical visualization and exploration of Latvian dialect features and supports research on dialect variation and the linguistic diversity of Latvian.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data collection is to document, preserve, and analyse the dialect diversity of the Latvian language. The collected data include dialect materials from fieldwork, dialect atlases, linguistic maps, and audio recordings. The interactive map provides a platform for visualising the geographical distribution of dialect features and supports research in dialectology and Baltic linguistics.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Textual data
- Coded textual data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- HTML
- CSV
- MP3
- JSON

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

Interactive Map of Latvian Dialects

Interactive Map of Latvian Dialects

<https://dialekti.lu.lv/>

id: null, Type: url

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Interactive Map of Latvian Dialects

Interactive Map of Latvian Dialects

<https://dialekti.lu.lv>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The data can be accessed through a standard web browser via the Interactive Map of Latvian Dialects (<https://dialekti.lu.lv/>). The platform provides a web-based interface for exploring dialect maps, linguistic data, and audio recordings.

Web browser

Any recent version

<https://dialekti.lu.lv/>

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

The data will remain accessible through the Interactive Map of Latvian Dialects (<https://dialekti.lu.lv/>). Most materials are publicly available, while some datasets may be accessible only to researchers due to copyright or data management restrictions. The platform ensures continued availability of dialect data, maps, and audio recordings after the end of the project.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Liene Markus-Narvila (0000-0001-9839-4586)

The sub-project leader oversees data management and compliance with the Data Management Plan.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Firewall

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Some dialect materials may have restrictions related to copyright and data management policies. In particular, certain audio recordings and research materials are accessible only to researchers. The data were collected following established research ethics practices.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Vietvārdu talka – Latvian Place Names Crowdsourcing Database

Apvidvārdu talka - Latvian Place Names Crowdsourcing Database - is a crowdsourcing platform developed by the Institute of the Latvian Language (University of Latvia) that allows members of the public to submit information about Latvian place names. The collected data contribute to the documentation, preservation, and research of Latvian toponyms, particularly locally used microtoponyms that are not always recorded in official maps or databases.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data collection is to document, preserve, and research Latvian place names. Through the crowdsourcing platform, members of the public can submit information about locally used place names, including microtoponyms that are often not recorded in official maps or databases. The collected data support research in toponymy, linguistics, geography, and cultural history.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Textual data
- Coded textual data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT

- JSON

- JPG

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Existing place-name datasets and cartographic sources have been considered; however, the aim of the platform is to collect new place-name data from the public, particularly locally used microtoponyms that are not recorded in existing databases or maps.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data are useful for researchers in toponymy, linguistics, geography, and cultural history. The collected place names contribute to documenting Latvian microtoponyms and local geographical terminology. The dataset may also be useful for historians, cartographers, local communities, and institutions interested in preserving cultural heritage and traditional place names.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The data can be accessed through a standard web browser via the "Vietvārdu talka" platform (<https://vietvardi.lu.lv/>). The platform provides a web-based interface for submitting and exploring Latvian place names and related information.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The data are stored and processed in widely used digital formats such as text, image, audio and structured database formats (e.g. TXT, CSV, JSON, JPG/PNG,

MP3). These formats are compatible with standard software applications and allow further processing and integration with other linguistic or geographical datasets.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Latvian toponymic terminology and place name classification

<https://vietvardi.lu.lv/>

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Place-name data are submitted by users through a crowdsourcing platform. The submitted information may require verification, and the data are subject to review and evaluation by researchers before they are used for research purposes.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Sanda Rapa (orcid: [0000-0002-7959-9719](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7959-9719))

The project leader oversees data management and compliance with the Data Management Plan.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The platform collects user-submitted place-name data. Any personal information provided by contributors is handled according to data protection regulations. Submitted entries are reviewed by researchers; if the information appears incorrect or unclear, researchers may contact the contributor for clarification. Entries containing incorrect or inappropriate information may be corrected or removed from the database.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Apvidvārdu talka – Latvian Regional Words Crowdsourcing

Database

Apvidvārdu talka - Latvian Regional Words Crowdsourcing Database - is a crowdsourcing platform developed by the Institute of the Latvian Language (University of Latvia) that allows members of the public to submit regional words used in different parts of Latvia. The platform supports the documentation and research of Latvian regional vocabulary and linguistic diversity.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data collection is to document and preserve Latvian regional vocabulary. Through the crowdsourcing platform “Apvidvārdu talka”, members of the public can submit regional words, their meanings, usage examples, and information about the region where they are used. The collected data support research in linguistics and dialectology.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Textual data
- Coded textual data
- Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV

- MP3

- JSON

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Existing linguistic resources and dictionaries of Latvian regional vocabulary have been considered. However, the aim of the platform "Apvidvārdu talka" is to collect new data from the public, particularly regional words and usage that may not be recorded in existing sources.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data will be useful for researchers in linguistics, dialectology, and cultural history. The collected regional words contribute to documenting Latvian regional vocabulary and linguistic diversity. The dataset may also be useful for educators, students, and local communities interested in preserving regional language heritage.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The data can be accessed through a standard web browser via the "Apvidvārdu talka" platform (<https://apvidvardi.lu.lv/>). The platform provides a web-based interface for submitting and exploring Latvian regional words and related information.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The data are stored and processed in widely used digital formats such as text, audio and structured database formats (e.g. TXT, CSV, JSON, MP3). These formats

are compatible with standard software applications and allow further processing and integration with other linguistic datasets.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

The collected data will remain accessible through the "Apvidvārdu talka" platform (<https://apvidvardi.lu.lv/>). The platform supports long-term access and reuse of Latvian regional vocabulary data for research and cultural heritage documentation.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

The platform collects user-submitted regional words. Submitted entries are reviewed by researchers; if the information is incorrect or unclear, contributors may be contacted for clarification, and incorrect entries may be corrected or removed from the database.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Sanda Rapa (orcid: [0000-0002-7959-9719](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7959-9719))

The project leader oversees data management and compliance with the Data Management Plan.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Firewall

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Some ethical and legal aspects may be relevant because the platform collects user-submitted information. Any personal information provided by contributors is handled according to data protection regulations. Submitted entries are reviewed by researchers, and contributors may be contacted to clarify the information. Incorrect entries may be corrected or removed from the database.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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